

Does Daily Commuting Matter to Employee Productivity?

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ABSTRACT

This study is the first of its kind to explore the relationship between commuting and employee productivity by drawing theories from multiple disciplines and empirical evidence from three Australian cities. Relying on a survey data from three major cities in Australia, this study finds that commuting distance is positively associated with absenteeism. This study also finds a positive association between active commuting (i.e., travel to work by walking or bicycling) and job performance in adults aged 35-54. The structural equation model further explored possible causal pathways from commuting to job productivity, and the results confirm that commuting mode choices and commuting distance influence absenteeism and job performance through affecting commuting satisfaction and personal health, though commuting distance retains a direct impact on absenteeism after controlling for the indirect effects. Overall, these findings support that commuting behaviors of employees influence their workplace productivity. Encourage active commuting not only improves the physical health of employees, but also enhances their job performance, contributing to economic benefits to employers.

Key words: daily commuting; employee productivity; commuting satisfaction; health; Australian cities

Introduction

Commuting is an important component of daily work activities, significantly contributing to the wellbeing of working population, yet its impact on employee productivity has surprisingly been little studied. Employee productivity (also referred to as workforce productivity) is broadly defined as the efficiency of a worker, and it is important for organizations and societies (Diener, 2012). Previous studies on employee productivity have primarily focused on the roles of the socio-demographic and attitudinal characteristics of employees and the cultural and environmental features of organizations (Liao and Chuang,

2004). There are increasing debates in both academia and industry with respect to how commuting might influence employee productivity. There are claims, for example, that workers with a long commute are more likely to be burned out, stressed and fall ill, and therefore more likely to be absent from work and perform poorly at work. There are also claims that workers who commute by walking and bicycling (defined as active commuters in this proposal) are more productive because of the health, cognitive and psychological benefits of active travel (Handy et al., 2014). Although these claims assume a causal relationship between commuting and productivity, studies that directly examine this relationship are quite sparse. Further, previous studies on travel behaviour have primarily focused on the health and environmental impacts; however, research that directly addresses the economic impact of travel behaviour is very scarce. This significantly limits our ability to make effective transport policies that aim to improve economic outcomes.

This study is the first of its kind to explore the relationship between commuting and employee productivity by drawing theories from multiple disciplines and empirical evidence from three Australian cities. Addressing this research question is particularly important for urban transportation policies. How to strategically plan the transportation network, and prioritise the limited resources (including right-of-way and transportation funding) to support a more sustainable and productive urban system have been the critical issues for local and state governments. However, current policy debates over transportation and productivity are primarily around moving people or goods to destinations in a cost-effective and timely manner, largely ignoring the potential impact of transportation on the activities undertaken at the destination. This study tackles this critical issue by specially addressing the impact of daily commuting on job activities.

How might commuting influence employee productivity?

Early work on the link between transportation and productivity has only been at the macro level, focusing on the impact of transportation infrastructure investment on economic productivity at state and national level. This type of work is usually framed into a traditional production function model, where transportation infrastructure is treated as a public capital, which like other inputs, such as private capital and labour that impact output. Transportation investment increases productivity by reducing travel costs and improving economies of agglomeration and economies of scale. Classical empirical studies include the work

conducted by Aschauer (1989) and Munnell (1990), who are among those economists enthusiastic on finding the reasons of substantial decline of productivity in the United States compared with the “golden age” of the 1950s and 1960s. These studies are important and have significant influence on the U.S. policies of infrastructure spending in the 1990s. However, these studies have primarily focused on the firm side with an economic input-output analysis at the macro level.

Very few studies have investigated the link between transportation and productivity that focused on employees and used behavioural mechanisms at individual levels. In the early urban economic models, work productivity is assumed to be independent from commuting because it is argued that commuting cost could be fully compensated by wage premiums or lower land rents so the commuting would not influence job satisfaction and performance. However, this early urban model rested on the premise that labour market is perfect and fully competitive. Until recently, a more realistic labour market, which allows for worker’s shirking behaviour (e.g., less working effort or absenteeism), was integrated into early urban economic models. This new combined model, namely urban efficiency wage model (Zenou, 2009), argues that workers make trade-offs between leisure time at home and effort in work, and therefore workers with long commutes would put in less effort or shirk work because of reduced leisure time (Ross and Zenou, 2008). This model provides a theoretical foundation in economics to model the relationship between commuting and work productivity. However, only one empirical study (Van Ommeren and Gutiérrez-i-Puigarnau, 2011) was found to have formally tested this theoretical hypothesis using a direct measure of shirking behaviour.

In addition to urban economics, other disciplines including public health, psychology, and brain science have also pointed out the possible paths that daily commuting could influence work productivity. First, a number of studies (Evans et al., 2002; Novaco et al., 1990; Wener et al., 2003) have established the link between commuting and mental stress, while commuting stress can further spill over into domains such as work performance and family relationships (Novaco et al., 1990; Wener et al., 2005). Further, it is well known that walking and bicycling for daily commuting could be important sources of physical activity, the lack of which is a major cause of obesity as well as other related chronic diseases (Bouchard et al., 2012). Obesity and chronic diseases significantly reduce workforce participation and increase absenteeism from work (Australian Institute of Health and Welfare, 2009). Therefore, commuting could affect work productivity through physical and mental health.

Second, a growing number of studies have found active commuting by walking and bicycling is perceived as more “relaxing and exciting” than commuting by car and public transport, which are perceived as being more “stressful and boring”. These positive or negative moods and emotions during the commuting influence moods and emotions during the work (Friman et al., 2017), thereby affecting work performance. Further, recent studies (Choi et al., 2013; Stutzer and Frey, 2008) also found that people with a longer commuting time report systematically lower subjective well-being than those with a shorter commute, and those who bike and walk to work are happier and more satisfied with life than public transport and car commuters (Martin et al., 2014). Given the strong evidence that happy people are more productive (Oswald et al., 2015), it is reasonable to hypothesize that active commuters and short-distance commuters would be more productive.

Finally, commuting mode choice might influence work productivity through cognitive ability. Physical activity is beneficial to brain function and cognition (Etnier et al., 1997; Hillman et al., 2008), which are related to the job performance of employees. It is, therefore, possible that active travel commuters might have better cognitive ability at work, at least in the first several hours of work after having an intense physical activity from bicycling and walking to work, and perform better than public transport and car commuters.

Although these possible pathways indicate that commuting might influence work productivity, little research has been conducted to formally test these hypotheses. This study aims to fill this research gap by providing strong empirical evidence from three Australian capital cities.

Methods

Data and Variables

The data was collected through an online survey conducted in May 2017. The study was limited to residents of three capital cities in Australia, Melbourne, Sydney and Brisbane, who are aged over 18 and full-time employed, have a fixed place of employment and make regular commute trips every week. Sample quotas were set up based on the population of each city. Participants of the survey were recruited through a local panel company. As the panel company provides a direct money incentive for the participants, for quality assurance purpose, two “trap” questions were added into the survey to identify the “speedster”. After cleaning the data, the number of valid responses is 1121. While the sample is not representative to the population, it covers a variety of employees in different industries and occupations (see Table 1).

Independent variables

The key interest of this study is to look at the impact of daily commute on employee productivity. Three commuting related variables were created, including commuting mode choice, commuting time and commuting distance. Commuting behavior was measured by asking respondents their primary mode used in the past month. Original mode choices include seven categories, including car/vanpool with other household member, car/vanpool with other, car/driving alone, walking, bicycling, bus/tram, and train. For simplicity, the first three modes were aggregated into one category (car), and the last two were combined into one category (transit). Respondents were also asked to report their commuting distance and usual commuting time (one-way). In addition to the commuting variables, this study also measured other variables that are possibly associated with productivity, including the employee's socio-demographic characteristics, their health condition, their job industry, their occupation, and the city where they reside. For health condition, both a self-reported measure on the overall health condition, and measures on level of physical activity using the questions adapted from International Physical Activity Questionnaire (IPAQ) (Craig et al., 2003) were used in this study.

Dependent variables

Employee productivity will be measured by absenteeism and job performance. Absenteeism is a commonly used and reasonable (inverse) measure of worker's productivity (Van Ommeren and Gutiérrez-i-Puigarnau, 2011). Both absenteeism and job performance measures were adapted from World Health Organization Health and Performance Questionnaire (HPQ), which has been validated and shows good concordance with archival (objective) performance measures from employers (Kessler et al., 2003). For absenteeism, HPQ asks number of whole and partial days absent for both health and other reasons in the past four weeks. For job performance, HPQ first asks a series of decomposition questions about critical aspects of work performance (e.g., how often the respondent did not work at times she/he was expected to be working, her/his work quality was lower than expected, she/he was daydreaming and not concentrating on work), and then uses a global rating scale to assess overall work performance in a given period. Comparing with other scales (e.g., Work Productivity Scale, Stanford Presenteeism) that are more relevant to white-collar workers than to blue-collar workers, HPQ ensures the questions on job performance equally apply across all occupations. In this study, the self-reported overall job performance in the

past month was used as a dependent variable which was coded using an ordered scale from zero to ten. Descriptive statistics of all variables are in Table 1.

Modeling methods

Given the nature of the dependent variables, negative binomial models were applied to predict absenteeism (called absenteeism model thereafter), while an ordered logit model was employed to predict overall job performance (called performance model thereafter). Two separate models were estimated for the two measures of absenteeism in order to further explore the two distinct behavior mechanism on how the commute may affect absenteeism. Following Van Ommeren and Gutiérrez-i-Puigarnau (2011), we also used the natural logarithm of commuting distance and commuting time in the models based on the assumption of diminishing marginal (dis)utility of commute. While commuting distance and time are highly correlated, they have different effects in absenteeism model and performance model. After comparing different model results, commuting distance was used in absenteeism models and commuting time was used in performance model for a better model fit. For commuting mode choice, transit was used as the reference group to compare with car, walking, and bicycling. For both models, socio-demographic characteristics, self-reported health condition and physical activity level of employees were controlled in the model, and dummies for industry, occupation and city were also included to account for unobserved heterogeneity between industries, occupations, and cities. As commuting might have different impact on cognitive functioning and therefore job performance for population at different age groups (Etnier et al., 1997), three separate models were estimated for younger adults (ages 18-34; n=338), middle-aged adults (ages 35-54; n=603) and older adults (ages 55-74; n=161) respectively to capture the variance of the effects.

Table 1 Descriptive statistics of variables (n=1121)

Variables	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
<i>Job performance</i>				
# days absent for health problems last month	0.70	2.06	0	28
# days absent for any other reason last month	1.00	2.71	0	31
Overall job performance last month	7.51	1.58	0	10
<i>Commuting characteristics</i>				
Commutated distance (km)	19.69	18.36	0	150
Commute time (minute)	36.41	23.58	1	180
Car	58%		0	1
Walk	6%		0	1
Bike	2%		0	1
Transit	34%		0	1
<i>Soio-demographics</i>				
Age (1=18-24; 2=25-34; 3=35-44; 4=45-54; 5=55-64; 6=65-74; 7=65+)	4.16	1.14	2	7
Female	51%		0	1
Annual Household Income (1=negative or zero; 2= \$1 - \$9,999; 3= \$10,000 - \$19,999; 4= \$20,000 - \$29,999; 5= \$30,000 - \$39,999; 6= \$40,000 - \$49,999; 7= \$50,000 - \$59,999; 8= \$60,000 - \$79,999; 9= \$80,000 - \$99,999; 10= \$100,000 - \$124,999; 11= \$125,000 - \$149,999; 12= \$150,000 - \$199,999; 13= \$200,000 or more)	9.73	2.19	1	13
Education (1= No qualifications; 2= Secondary school; 3= Tertiary (e.g., TAFE); 4= Undergraduate; 5= Graduate; 6= Postgraduate)	3.94	1.34	1	6
Health condition (1= Poor; 2=Fair; 3=Good; 4=Very good; 5=Excellent)	3.42	0.89	1	5
<i>Physical Activity (During the last 7 days, on how many days did you do the following activities for at least 10 minutes)</i>				
# walk days	4.23	2.38	0	7
# jog days	1.03	1.75	0	7
# hosework days	3.62	2.23	0	7
# garden days	1.00	1.49	0	7
# bike days	0.63	1.51	0	7
# exercise days	0.72	1.58	0	7
# workout days	0.95	1.72	0	7
# gym days	0.93	1.74	0	7
# TV/Computer/Video Games days	4.94	2.44	0	7
<i>Industry</i>				
Agriculture, Forestry and Fishing	0.3%		0	1
Mining	0.5%		0	1
Manufacturing	6.0%		0	1

Electricity, Gas, Water and Waste Servi	1.4%	0	1
Construction	4.0%	0	1
Wholesale trade	4.1%	0	1
Retail Trade	5.8%	0	1
Accommodation and Food Services	1.9%	0	1
Transport, Postal and Warehousing	4.9%	0	1
Information Media and Telecommunication	8.0%	0	1
Financial and Insurance Services	10.3%	0	1
Rental, Hiring and Real Estate Services	2.0%	0	1
Professional, Scientific and Technical	12.0%	0	1
Administrative and Support Services	5.7%	0	1
Public Administration and Safety	5.8%	0	1
Education and Training	8.8%	0	1
Health Care and Social Assistance	7.4%	0	1
Arts and Recreation Services	1.4%	0	1
Other Services	10.2%	0	1
Occupation		0	1
Executive, administrator, or senior man	11.1%	0	1
Professional (e.g., engineer, accountan	42.3%	0	1
Technical support (e.g., lab technician	6.8%	0	1
Sales (e.g., sales representative, stoc	7.7%	0	1
Operator or laborer (e.g., assembly lin	4.0%	0	1
Precision production and crafts worker	1.9%	0	1
Clerical and administrative support (e.	23.0%	0	1
Service occupation (e.g., security offi	3.2%	0	1
City		0	1
Sydney	36.6%	0	1
Melbourne	40.6%	0	1
Brisbane	22.8%	0	1

Results and Discussion

Results of two negative binomial models for absenteeism are reported in table 2. As expected and consistent with Van Ommeren and Gutiérrez-i-Puigarnau (2011), commuting distance is positively associated with the number of absent days for both health and other reasons. This suggests that commuting could influence absenteeism through both health and other mechanisms. First, workers with long commutes are more likely to get ill and therefore are more likely absent for health reasons. Second, workers with long commutes receive less net wage and less leisure time and therefore are more likely absent to avoid the commuting cost and time. To better illustrate the magnitude of impact of commuting distance on absenteeism, the predicted number of days absent at different commuting distance scenarios were estimated and plotted in Figure 1, while holding all other independent variables at their mean values. Using workers with a (one-way) commuting distance of 15 km (average commuting distance for Australian capital cities) as a reference group, workers with a commuting

distance of 1 km have 36% and 45% lower (expected) absent days for health and other reasons respectively, while workers with a commuting distance of 50 km have 22% and 30% higher (expected) absent days for health and other reasons respectively. Commuting modes were not associated with absenteeism in both models, although active travel commuters were hypothesized to have less absent days because of the health benefits from active travel.

In addition to commuting variables, some socio-demographic variables were significantly associated with absenteeism. Female adults, for example, are more likely to be absent from work for other reasons but not for health problems, and this might be associated with the more family responsibilities of women and a more acceptable social culture for women absence (REF).

Table 2 Negative binomial models for absenteeism

	# days absent for health problems			# days absent for any other reason		
	Coef.	z		Coef.	z	
Car	-0.143	-0.860		-0.106	-0.610	
Walk	0.065	0.170		0.065	0.180	
Bike	-0.812	-1.370		0.166	0.310	
Commute distance (in log)	0.162	2.100	**	0.221	2.960	***
Age	-0.018	-0.260		-0.095	-1.300	
Female	0.143	0.940		0.266	1.600	*
Income	0.045	1.200		0.072	2.080	**
Education	-0.037	-0.590		0.065	1.010	
Health condition	-0.410	-5.210	***	-0.127	-1.410	
Industry dummies	included			included		
City dummies	included			included		
Occupation dummies	included			included		
Physical activity	included			included		
Number of obs.	1102			1102		
McFadden's R2:	0.037			0.029		
Log-Lik. Intercept Only	-1179.7			-1348.0		
Log-Lik. Full Model	-1135.5			-1309.4		

*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01

Figure 1 Predicted number of days absent

Model results suggest different associations between commuting behavior and job performance among different age groups. For employees aged 35-54, bicycling ($b=1.0$, $OR=2.71$, $p<.05$), walking ($b=.71$, $OR=2.04$, $p<.05$) and car commuters ($b=.37$, $OR=1.45$, $p<.05$) were significantly higher in job performance than transit commuters, after controlling for socio-demographic characteristics of the employees and industries they work in. However, the significant relationships were not found in the younger (aged 18-34) and older (aged 55-74) age group. In addition, commuting time was significantly associated with job performance ($b=-.016$, $OR=.98$, $p<.01$) in younger age group but not in other two groups. For job satisfaction, commuting time had a significantly negative effect, and this was consistent among the age groups. Walking commuters had significantly higher job satisfaction ($b=.81$, $OR=2.25$, $p<.05$) comparing with transit commuters in middle aged group (35-64), while car commuters had significantly lower ($b=-.93$, $OR=.40$, $p<.05$) job satisfaction comparing with transit commuters in older age group. Finally, there were strong associations between commuting satisfaction, job satisfaction and job performance.

Table 3 Ordered logit models for job performance

	Age: 18-34		Age: 35-54		Age: 55-74	
	Coef.	z	Coef.	z	Coef.	z
Car	0.401	1.490	0.369	1.920 *	-0.429	-0.930

Walk	0.181	0.390		0.687	1.830	*	-0.770	-0.860
Bike	-0.096	-0.090		1.544	2.530	**	-0.933	-0.760
Commute time (in log)	-0.295	-1.740	*	0.086	0.720		-0.091	-0.370
Age	-0.402	-1.410		0.600	3.700	***	0.717	1.140
Female	-0.112	-0.490		0.117	0.710		1.019	2.540
Income	0.076	1.540		0.036	0.970		0.057	0.600
Education	0.048	0.470		0.040	0.610		-0.099	-0.660
Health condition	0.319	2.400	**	0.551	5.860	***	0.245	1.230
Industry dummies	included			included			included	
City dummies	included			included			included	
Occupation dummies	included			included			included	
Physical activity	included			included			included	
Number of obs.	338			603			161	
McFadden's R2:	0.066			0.062			0.100	
Log-Lik. Intercept Only	-607.97			-1058			-272.08	
Log-Lik. Full Model	-567.65			-991.88			-244.87	

*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01

Conclusions

This study finds a positive association between active commuting (i.e., travel to work by walking or bicycling) and job performance in adults aged 35-54. Further, this study finds commuting time is negatively associated with job satisfaction. Overall, commuting behaviors of employees influence their workplace performance. Cross-sectional nature of this study limits the causal reference.

Implications for Practice and Policy

Encourage active commuting not only improves physical health of employees, but also enhances their job performance, contributing to economic benefits to employers. Commuting related strategies should be considered in employers' overall strategy for improving job performance. These strategies should aim to promote active commuting and shorten commuting time.

The evidence produced by this comparison contributes to the urban planning field and to practice and policy in several ways. First, this research makes a significant contribution to theories in travel behaviour and urban planning and provides new empirical insights into how and to what extent commuting behaviour contributes to employee productivity. Second, the research is expected to benefit government agencies in providing robust empirical evidence to inform transport policies on workforce productivity and justifications of transportation resources allocation. Third, this research is also expected to benefit employers in offering

evidence-based strategies for managing employees' commuting behaviour to improve overall organizational productivity. Finally, improving urban productivity is central to the Australian Government's Smart Cities Plan, and this study will contribute to this smart cities agenda from the perspectives of transportation and urban planning.

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